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Ecotherapy as a mental health promotion intervention in young adults

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Abstract

Background: Ecotherapy, a growing field within applied environmental psychology, utilizes human–nature interaction as a pathway to mental health and mental well-being. Although prior research has demonstrated the mental health benefits of physical immersion in natural environments, less is known about the effects of indirect or digital nature exposure in structured academic contexts.

Objective: This study examined the psychological impact of a classroom-based, digital ecotherapeutic intervention featuring nature imagery and soundscapes on the mental well-being and anxiety levels of university students.

Methods: A pre-post intervention design was implemented with a sample of 110 undergraduate students. During the second half of the academic semester, nature-based audiovisual material was integrated into weekly lectures. Psychological outcomes were assessed using two validated instruments: the Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) and the Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) scale.

Results: Statistically significant improvements were observed in four domains of mental well-being: relaxation, cheerfulness, optimism about the future, and energy to spare ($p < .05$). Several additional indicators showed non-significant positive trends. While GAD-7 scores did not significantly change, some items demonstrated a positive trend suggesting a possible buffering effect against academic stress.

Conclusion: The findings support the effectiveness of digital ecotherapeutic interventions in enhancing student mental health well-being, even within indoor academic settings. The intervention's low cost and easy integration into educational contexts position it as a promising tool for mental health promotion in higher education. This study contributes to expanding ecotherapy beyond natural immersion, offering scalable alternatives for psychological support within urbanized and institutional environments.

Keywords: Ecotherapy; Mental Health Promotion; Mental Well-Being; Anxiety; Digital Ecotherapy; Young Adults' Higher Education

1. Introduction

High stress and a detachment from nature define the modern way of life, which greatly affects the mental well-being of many people [1, 2]. There is increasing need for different methods that support emotional balance and general mental health, especially in educational settings under performance pressure and unrelenting stress for both students and teachers [3] Ecotherapy, a therapeutic approach that aims to reestablish a connection between people and nature, has been demonstrated to benefit mental health since exposure to natural environments reduces stress and increases

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positive emotions [4, 5]. However, direct access to natural environments is often limited for people living in cities or those learning inside confined. Digital ecotherapy offers a sustainable solution by recreating nature's sights and sounds, with studies indicating that even this "digital nature" can improve mood and focus [6, 7].

Mental disorders affect nearly 1 billion people globally, representing a big portion of the world's total disease burden [8, 9, 10]. Whether good or bad, stress is a natural part of college life. Though it may be a motivator, stress can also be detrimental. Chronic stress is harmful. Elevated stress levels over time suppress immune functions and raise adrenaline, blood pressure, muscular tension, and heart rate [11, 12].

A creative illustration of digital ecotherapy can be used in learning environments to improve mental well-being [13]. Digital ecotherapy stands out as a sustainable approach to promote mental well-being and improve emotional regulation and mental health in educational and other settings in a society where natural interaction is sometimes restricted.

This research is an example of digital ecotherapy applied in educational settings to promote mental health and mental well-being among students [13]. This intervention uses digital tools to display natural landscapes and play nature sounds, creating a calming environment for participants. Participants experience the benefits of nature even when indoors, which may help reduce stress and improve focus and concentration [7].

1.1. Ecotherapy

The term "ecotherapy," first coined by psychotherapist Howard Clinebell in 1996, refers to therapeutic techniques grounded in nature to improve mental well-being [14]. While definitions vary, a consensus exists that ecotherapy encompasses systematic, nature-based practices designed to produce preventive and restorative health outcomes [15, 16, 17].

Its techniques are diverse, ranging from active interventions like therapeutic gardening and green exercise to more passive experiences such as landscape viewing, all aimed at improving relaxation, focus, and social connection [18, 19]. This approach gained traction with the rise of environmental concerns, and a significant body of research now links insufficient green space with an elevated risk for mental health disorders [20, 21, 22, 23, 24].

1.2. Theoretical Background of Ecotherapy

1.2.1. Attention Restoration Theory (ART) (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989) [25]

The theory posits that exposure to nature can restore and rejuvenate our cognitive functions, particularly our directed attention, which can become depleted over time due to overuse and fatigue. According to Kaplans, there are two types of attention. Directed Attention: This refers to the cognitive ability to concentrate on a specific task while ignoring distractions. Involuntary Attention (or Fascination): This type of attention requires no cognitive effort and is automatically drawn by interesting stimuli. According to ART, natural environments offer "soft" or "gentle" fascinations.

1.2.2. The Biophilia Hypothesis (Wilson, 1986) [26]

According to this hypothesis, humans have an innate tendency to seek connection with nature and other forms of life. The hypothesis is based on the idea that our love for nature is embedded in our very biology. Wilson argues that this evolutionary predisposition continues to shape our behavior even today, even though the natural environment no longer plays a direct role in our daily survival. Furthermore, the Biophilia Hypothesis suggests that because our brain developed as an adaptive response to nature, it functions better in natural environments or in settings that mimic natural characteristics. This is why activities like gardening, hiking in the forest, and swimming reduce stress, improve mood, and generally promote mental and physical well-being.

1.2.3. Stress recovery theory or SRT

Stress recovery theory enhances people's understanding and application of ecotherapy. It emphasizes the significance of nature in the relief of stress. Stress reduction rapidly occurs through the healing processes of the mind and body through natural settings, as posited by SRT. The studies by Ulrich [1, 27] found that any form of exposure to natural settings, such as through window view of a garden, walking in a park and even interacting with green sloped areas helps in lowering blood pressure. Also, it reduces muscle tension and increases general physiological relaxation. Ulrich investigated the psychological impact of viewing natural sceneries on student stress [28, 29, 30] and on medical recovery rates [1]. His research revealed alterations in mental states following students' observation of "natural" scenes linked to the environment. These scenes enhanced positive emotions of affection, friendliness, elation, and playfulness.

Exposure to non-nature-based views, such as urban environments, predominantly elicited a singular emotion: sadness. Observing urban environments sometimes heightened hostility and anger, whereas watching natural settings typically diminished these emotions. Natural landscapes and ecosystems promote positive emotions while reducing anger and aggressiveness. Through SRT ecotherapy is a process of psychotherapy that fits itself into the mental health system. By including encounters with natural surroundings in the treatment plans, including using parks for therapy, viewing nature landscapes, ecotherapy conditions individuals in ways that induce relaxation, secure grounding, inner peace, and an increased sense of wellness. It has been found that connecting with nature may also help individuals express emotions and attain clear; state of mind decreasing levels of stress and anxiety [31].

1.3. Ecotherapy and Mental health/Mental Well-being

In 1984, environmental psychologist Robert Ulrich authored research entitled "View Through a Window May Influence Recovery from Surgery." [1] Ulrich's research indicates that patients who observed trees during their treatment have reduced healing times. Since then, numerous studies have aimed to elucidate the relationship between patients' recovery and their time spent in nature. However, ecotherapy interventions have only recently been developed and implemented by physicians as primary or adjunctive treatments for the management and treatment of mental disorders [17, 32]. Ecotherapy is an emerging treatment method that utilizes various approaches to leverage the therapeutic benefits of nature.

1.4. Mental health in adolescents and young adults

The incidence of anxiety and mood disorders has shown an alarming increase among adolescents and young adults, particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting social isolation [33]. Adolescence and early adulthood are periods marked by intense psychosocial transitions, making young people especially vulnerable to anxiety, which often goes unrecognized or unmanaged [34]. Academic pressures, social norms, future uncertainty, and excessive technology use exacerbate the phenomenon [35]. Salari et al. (2020) in A systematic review and Meta-Analysis found that the global prevalence of anxiety during the pandemic was 31.9%, and that of depression 33.7% of the population [36]. The study emphasized the pandemic's negative psychological impact, particularly in the general population. During the covid-19 pandemic several studies [31, 37] showed that ecotherapy practices improved the symptomatology of mental health disorders and generally promote mental well-being. Due to the above, more and more attention has been given by researchers to investigating the benefits of ecotherapy in the promotion of mental health and well-being.

1.5. Ecotherapy and perceived self-esteem and quality of life

There are not many studies on how exposure to nature affects self-esteem and quality of life. Recent research of urban and rural Lithuanian people found a link between quality of life and nature exposure, mediated by nature connection [38]. A thorough assessment revealed improved quality of life in those with a physical condition after restorative or physical activities in natural environments [39]. People in green environments who were physically active for at least five minutes reported higher self-esteem in different research [40]. Moreover, research shows that university students who spend 20 minutes a week in a natural environment of their choice report greater life satisfaction after exposure to nature [41].

1.6. Ecotherapy Lowers Stress

Participating in a green outdoor setting can be a fast and effective way to reduce persistent stress and improve mental health and positive emotions [42]. Extensive studies show that time spent in green settings, such as parks and woods, as well as simulated natural environments, can reduce stress symptoms [43], improve psychological resilience under stress [44], lower blood pressure [45], and reduce anger. Interactions with nature can inspire wonder and improve mental well-being [46]. Exposure to outdoors might increase cognitive function and focus—benefits that might particularly attract college students. A study by Lohr et al. (1996) found that the simple addition of plants into a computer lab reduced stress, improved focus, and increased college student output by 12% [47]. Natural views, on the other hand, improve the capacity to focus attention [48].

1.7. Ecotherapy regulates mood and fosters positive emotions.

A number of studies have indicated that ecotherapy can lower stress and diminish anxiety and melancholy symptoms for those coping with life's challenges. For instance, Vivian (2018) looked at several ecotherapy studies and found encouraging outcomes in its capacity to produce positive emotions including pleasure, playfulness, and warmth [49]. By fostering emotional resilience, these feelings help to offset the negative effects of mental health problems or diseases. Programs on forest immersion can significantly reduce cortisol levels, according to Putri et al. (2023), thereby stabilizing mood and enhancing general well-being [50]. Moreover, these initiatives motivate people to concentrate on

their natural environment and pause stressful or monotonous thinking. According to Delaney and Hogan (2019), ecotherapy activates brain regions linked to relaxation and pleasure by combining mental health strategies with therapeutic exposure to nature [51]. Furthermore, certain types of ecotherapy enhance social connections, which are crucial for mental well-being. Ibes et al. (2018) found that taking part in group activities in natural settings lifts mood and lowers feelings of loneliness and isolation [52]. These events increase self-esteem and overall emotional well-being by encouraging significant social contacts. For instance, community gardening has been recognized as a successful way to promote cooperation and foster a feeling of purpose and connection.

1.8. Ecotherapy in the digital age

Often known as green treatment or nature-based approach, ecotherapy stresses the healing benefits of interacting with nature. Traditional ecotherapy reduces stress and fosters mental well-being by using natural environments like forests or gardens [53]. Digital ecotherapy modifies this method to mimic natural experiences using tools such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and multimedia apps [54]. For those unable to reach natural settings because of urbanization, transportation concerns, or other limitations, this modality provides individualized therapeutic experiences such as virtual forest walks or ocean view meditations [55]. Digital ecotherapy uses virtual settings, natural sounds, and interactive material to provide sensory stimulation. For example, immersive VR systems mimic natural settings that elicit good psychological reactions including lower stress and augmenting feelings of happiness [56]. These devices produce healing experiences by activating the same cognitive and emotional pathways as direct contact to nature [52]. Studies show that digital ecotherapy helps to promote mental health and mental well-being. Virtual green spaces have shown the ability to reduce cortisol levels, a biomarker of stress, and enhance mood states in both clinical and non-clinical populations [56].

A comprehensive review [66] indicated that digital ecotherapy treatments are up to a certain degree similar to conventional cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) in lowering feelings of anxiety and sadness. Programs incorporating digital ecotherapy into treatment plans claim better emotional control and higher general well-being. For example, hospitals using virtual forest treatment in waiting rooms reported notable decreases in patient tension and anxiety [55]. Key benefits of digital ecotherapy are its accessibility, scalability, and affordability. Urban and underprivileged communities may gain access to rehabilitative tools once reserved for people near natural settings. Moreover, its adaptable form encourages regular usage by means of incorporation into daily activities [54]. In a world where natural contact is often limited, digital ecotherapy emerges as a sustainable solution for promoting mental well-being and improving mental health in educational and other environments. On a social level, digital ecotherapy offers inexpensive solutions that may reach big populations, hence addressing inequalities in mental health treatment. It also fits with the worldwide movement toward preventative health policies and the use of digital technologies in medical practice [52].

The importance of digital technologies in the field of Ecotherapy and education is highlighted in this paragraph. ICTs support universal access to education, provide innovative approaches for effective teacher training, enhance learning retention, promote cooperation, increase openness, develop learner-centered approaches, and hasten the process of learning. Additionally, by using virtualization, mobilization, artificial intelligence, and new learning environments like virtual worlds, support educational activities and methodologies. More specifically, ICTs are very effective and productive in ADHD training, facilitating and improving assessment, intervention, and educational procedures via mobile devices that bring educational activities everywhere [100-103] and through a variety of ICT applications that serve as the backbone of education [104-116]. The use of AI, STEM, and robotics raises educational practices to new levels of flexibility, innovation, and performance [117-121], while games turn education into a multimodal, incredibly amiable, and pleasurable engagement [122-124]. Moreover, the adoption, improvement, and fusion of ICTs with theories and models of metacognition, mindfulness, meditation, and emotional intelligence cultivation [125-141] places the development of mental abilities at the center of educational procedures and policies, which accelerates and improves educational practices and outcomes, particularly in ecotherapy domain.

1.9. Skyros Project: from knowledge to action

A multi-awarded project - that focuses on ecotherapy, environmental awareness and communication - the Skyros Project was founded by the "Environmental Education, Training, and Communication Research Unit" of the University of West Attica working with the Skyros Port Fund [58]. The project also features the active involvement of the Skyros Municipality from 2024 [59]. A well-organized summer program run by competent environmental teachers on the island of Skyros has shown great promise as a suitable vehicle for climate change communication. Data from pre- and post-program interviews shows that this project changes participants' knowledge, attitudes, and involvement on climate-related concerns. After participating in the program, participants said they felt more fulfilled in helping environmental conservation [60]. The Academy's fundamental belief is that if sustainability is taught and understood as a more general word that signifies healthy people inside a healthy community within a healthy environment, it may

greatly influence people's lives. The scientific placement of this study within the project's umbrella is justified by converging among its key goals such as fostering psychological resilience, promoting mental well-being through ecotherapy approaches, teaching environmental awareness and pro-environmental behavior, as well as the aims of the present inquiry. As a model for scalable, human-centered environmental innovation, this contextual embeddedness promotes the interdisciplinary objective of the Skyros Project.

2. Methodology

2.1. Recruitment and Participants

This study was conducted over a period of 13 weeks, from 09/10/2024 when the first phase of data collection was conducted, until 22/01/2025 when the second round of data collection took place. The study involved 110 university students, aged 18 and older, enrolled in the Department of Public and Community Health at the University of West Attica, Greece. Participants were selected based on their registration in the « Counseling and Communication Skills» course during the winter academic semester of 2024-2025. Recruitment was carried out by inviting students who had included this course in their schedule, with data collection occurring during the scheduled lecture sessions. The ethical integrity of the study was maintained through adherence to established research guidelines. All participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures before giving informed consent. The anonymity of respondents was safeguarded by excluding personal identifiers from the dataset and ensuring secure data storage.

2.2. Intervention

The intervention involved an ecotherapy-based approach using natural audiovisual material to enhance mental well-being. The intervention was introduced one week before the first data collection phase. Participants were informed about the study both verbally during a lecture and via an announcement posted on the course's e-class platform. They were informed that they would be asked to complete two sets of questionnaires during the course sessions. The first data collection phase took place during the first lecture on 09/10/2024, in a lecture hall at the University of West Attica. A total of 110 students attended the session, where they were provided with the questionnaires.

The second phase of data collection occurred at the end of the semester, on 22/01/2025 in the same lecture hall. Participants were once again notified via e-class and orally during the previous lecture. A total of 110 students attended the second session and completed the questionnaires. For each phase, before distributing the questionnaires, participants were informed in detail about the nature of the study. They were asked to complete the first and second questionnaires (the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) and Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale (GAD-7) in the designated order. Each questionnaire was completed individually in a controlled environment to ensure proper focus.

The questionnaires were completed on average in around 5 minutes. Following the first set of questionnaires, the lectures started as usual. The last 6 lectures took place along with a projector showing shown nature-based audiovisual material, including videos of natural landscapes such as oceans, forests, rain, accompanied by natural soundscapes, including bird songs and ocean waves. This audiovisual intervention was designed to simulate exposure to nature, following the principles of Attention Restoration Theory (ART) [25]. The content was projected using a projector in the lecture hall with participants instructed to turn off their mobile phones or set them to airplane mode. The audiovisual material was shown during the lecture, lasting for a period of 120 minutes with a 20-minute break, corresponding to the duration of the class.

The intervention continued throughout the semester, with participants being exposed to the audiovisual content during each lecture. This repeated exposure aimed to enhance the restorative effects of nature on mental well-being. The source of the material was an edited "film" of different videos from "YouTube" which were copyright free. After the intervention, participants were once again asked to complete the same two questionnaires at the second data collection session at the end of the semester. The process was the same as the first phase, with participants given clear instructions and time to complete the questionnaires. The average time for completing the second set of questionnaires was 5 minutes.

2.3. Data Collection

Mental well-being was measured using the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) and Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale (GAD-7). Both scales are self-reported, structured questionnaires with Likert-type scales that assess emotional states over the preceding two weeks. WEMWBS is a 14-item scale designed to measure mental well-

being, focusing on positive emotions and life satisfaction. It includes statements such as "I've been feeling optimistic about the future," and participants rate how often they have experienced each feeling on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = "Never" to 5 = "Always" [61]. The Greek version was translated and standardized by Petrogiannis et al. (2024) [62].

What WEMWBS measures

- Positive emotions: Evaluates feelings of joy, happiness, and contentment.
- Optimism and positive outlook: Assesses a positive attitude and optimism about the future.
- Resilience and self-esteem: Measures self-esteem, confidence, and the ability to cope with challenges.
- Sense of purpose and meaning: Assesses the sense of purpose and meaning in life.
- Social functioning: Evaluates positive social relationships and the ability to build and maintain relationships.
- General well-being: Provides an overall assessment of mental well-being.

GAD-7 is a 7-item scale used to assess symptoms of generalized anxiety disorder. The Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) [63, 64, 65] is a brief, valid, and reliable self-report screening tool consisting of seven items designed to identify the presence of generalized anxiety disorder (GAD). Participants are asked to indicate how frequently they have experienced symptoms described in each statement over the past two weeks, using a 4-point Likert scale. The response options—"Not at all", "Several days", "More than half the days", and "Nearly every day"—are scored as 0, 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

It should be noted that GAD-7 [66, 67] limitation is that it was specifically designed to identify symptoms of Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) based on the DSM-IV-TR diagnostic criteria [62, 68], rather than to function as a comprehensive assessment of anxiety symptoms in general populations. The seven questions are closely linked to the fundamental characteristics of Generalized Anxiety condition (GAD), including excessive concern, restlessness, exhaustion, and concentration difficulties, therefore limiting its diagnostic applicability to that specific condition. As a result, its sensitivity for detecting various anxiety disorders (i.e. panic disorder, social anxiety disorder) it is not very strong [69].

More importantly, the GAD-7 exhibits a somewhat diminished ability to detect subclinical or non-disorder-specific anxiety symptoms, that are not present at the respected diagnostic criteria of the DSM-IV-TR prevalent in the general populace, which may nonetheless correlate with considerable suffering or functional impairment. This limited emphasis, diminishes to a certain degree its efficacy to embrace the whole range of anxiety-related feelings, especially in cases where the focus is not to achieve a diagnosis. The diagnostic meta-analysis conducted by [69] highlights this limitation, asserting that although the GAD-7 functions satisfactorily as a case-finding instrument for Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD), its precision declines when utilized for the wider classification of "any anxiety disorder" or for milder, non-clinical manifestations.

The total GAD-7 scores range from 0 to 21, with higher scores indicating more severe symptoms of generalized anxiety: 0–4: Minimal anxiety, 5–9: Mild anxiety, 10–14: Moderate anxiety, 15–21: Severe anxiety. No specific authorization was required for the use of the Greek-language validated version of the GAD-7 scale in this study. Before completing the primary mental well-being questionnaires, participants provided demographic information through a short survey, which included questions about their gender (male, female, other, prefer not to answer), age group (18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54), and employment status (currently employed: yes/no).

2.4. Study Design

The design of the study was pre- and post-test, within subjects. The same group of students was assessed at two points: before and after the intervention. This design allowed us to compare the mental well-being and anxiety scores of participants within the same cohort, controlling for between-subject variability.

Although the intervention followed a pre-post design, attendance records revealed that not all participants who completed the baseline assessments were present at the final session, and vice versa. Therefore, paired data were not available for all individuals, and analyses were conducted on the matched subset, while descriptive comparisons included the full samples from both time points.

As part of the follow-up process, the attendance data from the course's official roll call was used to determine how many participants who attended the first data collection phase also participated in the second phase. This step helped verify the consistency of participation across both phases of data collection.

The intervention was conducted in a group setting, and data collection was done in a lecture hall, ensuring that all participants were exposed to the same environmental conditions during both phases of the study. The use of nature-based audiovisual material as an intervention aimed to trigger the psychological benefits outlined in Attention Restoration Theory and the Biophilia Hypothesis, which suggest that exposure to natural stimuli can improve mood, reduce mental fatigue, and enhance attention [25, 70].

The collected data from the WEMWBS and GAD-7 questionnaires were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 28.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant demographics and baseline measures. Independent samples t-tests were employed to compare pre- and post-intervention scores on the WEMWBS and GAD-7 scales. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$ for all comparisons.

3. Results

The study included 110 participants. Their basic demographic characteristics are displayed in the graphs below. The age distribution consisted of participants aged 18-24, at 91.8%, with only 2.8% falling into the 25-34 age group. Each of the remaining age groups (35-44, 45-54 and 55-64) accounted for 1.8% of the sample. The target population of this study, which was university students especially, is reflected in this age distribution.

Figure 1 Age Groups Included in the Study

Regarding the gender distribution in this survey, the majority of respondents identified as female (76.9%), while 20.9% identified as male. Of them, 0.9% preferred not to disclose their gender, while 2.7% of them identified as "other".

Figure 2 Gender Distribution of Participants

Finally, they were asked about their employment status and 63.6% responded that they were not currently employed, while the remaining 36.4% were currently employed.

Figure 3 Employment Status of Participants

In both instruments, descriptive statistics were calculated for each item. The Warwick-Edinburgh Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS) showed an overall improvement in well-being, with mean scores increasing from $M = 3.56$ $SD = 1.03$ pre-test to $M = 3.69$, $SD = 0.96$ post-test. Similarly, mean scores on the Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD-7) scale decreased from $M = 1.56$, $SD = 1.60$ to $M = 0.92$, $SD = 0.84$, indicating a general improvement in reported anxiety symptoms. The mean differences indicated that most items showed a trend towards positive change, but only four items showed statistically significant changes. Based on the results of the pre- and post-intervention questionnaire, the descriptive statistics for the two main categories of stress and well-being are shown in the table below.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of the Variables Examined

Variables	Pre (M)	Post (M)	Pre (SD)	Post (SD)	p
Mental Well-being					
Feeling optimistic about the future	3.39	3.62	0.98	0.98	0.04
Feeling useful	3.78	3.82	0.98	0.97	0.39
Feeling relaxed	2.67	2.99	1.08	1.14	0.02
Feeling interested in other people	4.28	4.38	0.96	0.77	0.19
Having energy to spare	3.56	3.80	1.15	1.00	0.04
Dealing with problems well	3.39	3.48	1.01	0.83	0.23
Thinking clearly	3.35	3.52	1.12	1.08	0.12
Feeling good about myself	3.39	3.41	1.14	1.11	0.45
Feeling close to other people	3.70	3.79	1.02	0.92	0.24
Feeling confident	3.30	3.44	1.09	1.06	0.17
Being able to make up my own mind about things	3.56	3.66	1.03	0.88	0.22
Feeling loved	3.85	3.92	1.07	1.01	0.33
Being interested in new things	4.21	4.23	0.81	0.80	0.44
Feeling cheerful	3.43	3.66	1.03	0.92	0.04

Table 2 Stress

Feeling nervous, anxious, or on edge	1.90	1.81	0.84	0.64	0.19
Not being able to control worrying	1.35	1.48	0.97	0.82	0.15
Worrying too much about different things	1.81	1.95	0.86	0.82	0.12
Trouble relaxing	1.57	1.55	0.88	0.78	0.43
Being so restless that it's hard to sit still	1.31	1.32	1.01	1.00	0.47
Becoming easily annoyed or irritable	1.74	1.70	0.88	0.86	0.37
Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen	1.25	1.39	1.02	0.97	0.38

The results of the intervention indicate a statistically significant improvement in several indicators of mental and emotional well-being. Specifically, the mean score for *feeling optimistic about the future* increased from 3.39 to 3.62 ($t = -1.72, p = 0.043$), showing that participants felt more optimistic after the intervention. This increase was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a positive impact on their outlook.

Similarly, the mean score for *feeling relaxed* rose from 2.67 to 2.99 ($t = -2.13, p = 0.017$), also reflecting a significant improvement. This finding indicates that participants were more able to relax following the intervention, which may point to reduced stress levels and better emotional regulation.

Moreover, the *sense of having energy to spare* improved as well, with the mean score rising from 3.54 to 3.80 ($t = -1.82, p = 0.035$). This suggests that participants felt more energized, which could be associated with enhanced physical and psychological well-being.

Finally, the mean score for *feeling cheerful* increased from 3.43 to 3.66 ($t = -1.80, p = 0.037$), again a statistically significant change. This indicates an improvement in mood and overall emotional state.

The analysis of additional well-being and anxiety-related variables revealed some positive trends, though none reached statistical significance. The mean score for *feeling interested in other people* increased from 4.28 (SD = 0.96) to 4.38 (SD = 0.77), representing a small yet positive change.

Figure 4 Percentages of Participants Reporting Interest in Other People (Pre and Post Intervention)

Similarly, the mean score for *thinking clearly* rose from 3.35 (SD = 1.12) to 3.52 (SD = 1.08), indicating a slight improvement in mental clarity.

Figure 5 Percentages of Participants Reporting Clear Thinking (Pre and Post Intervention)

In terms of *feeling confident*, the mean score increased from 3.30 (SD = 1.09) to 3.44 (SD = 1.06), reflecting a modest improvement in self-esteem.

Figure 6 Percentages of Participants Reporting Confidence (Pre and Post Intervention)

Regarding anxiety-related measures, the mean score for *not being able to control worrying* increased slightly from 1.35 (SD = 0.97) to 1.48 (SD = 0.82), reflecting a mild increase in the perceived inability to manage anxiety.

Figure 7 Percentages Reporting Inability to Stop or Control Worrying (Pre and Post Intervention)

Similarly, the mean score for *worrying too much about different things* rose from 1.81 (SD = 0.86) to 1.95 (SD = 0.82).

Figure 8 Percentages Reporting Excessive Worry About Different Things (Pre and Post Intervention)

Lastly, the mean score for *feeling afraid that something awful might happen* increased from 1.25 (SD = 1.02) to 1.39 (SD = 0.97), suggesting a slight rise in perceived insecurity or fear. The decrease in standard deviation (from 1.02 to 0.97) may indicate less variation in participants' emotional responses to fear after the intervention.

Figure 9 Percentages Reporting Fear That Something Awful Might Happen (Pre and Post Intervention)

4. Discussion

The results of the current study provide strong proof that a digital ecotherapeutic intervention may greatly improve important aspects of mental health and mental well-being among younger adults, specifically university students. Participants experienced statistically significant increases in feelings of relaxation, future optimism, cheerfulness, and perceived energy four separates yet related psychological resources known to protect against stress and help manifest emotional resilience [3, 71, 72]. These results are in accordance with the theoretical models of Stress Reduction Theory (SRT) [73] and Attention Restoration Theory (ART) [25].

Though the intervention took place indoors and relied on audiovisual digital stimuli its measurable effects suggest that digital ecotherapy is an intervention capable of promoting mental health and a sense of well-being [74]. It should be emphasized that the post-intervention evaluation fell near the end of the academic semester, a time that is linked with increased stress from approaching examinations.

Previous studies show that university students show significant rises in anxiety, cognitive stress, and emotional dysregulation around test times [75, 76]. At this point, therefore, it would have been rational to anticipate an increase in worry and a decline in psychological well-being. The results' indication of stable or perhaps somewhat better anxiety

scores and robust well-being scores in 4 items in spite of the impending examinations gives further interpretative value to the protective function of this ecotherapeutic intervention.

The significant rise of optimism about the future indicates an enhanced positive orientation about the future and a sense of hope. According to some studies [77], optimism functions as a protective barrier against anxiety and depressive symptomatology [78]. Optimism often reflects agency thinking, which means goal directed thinking and behavior. Along the same lines, it can be supported that optimism can also mean higher motivation to achieve goals and construct plans. These findings suggest that even artificial exposure to audio-visual natural stimuli can promote an adaptive orientation. The rise in the feeling of optimism discovered in this study could indicate a renewed feeling of potential and continuity among participants, symbolically triggered by the environmental stimuli views of landscapes, running water, sunlight, or plant life. Consistent with the Biophilia Hypothesis [70], these components have profound evolutionary and psychological significance linked to development, rebirth, and advancement. Particularly in populations that are going through transformative developmental phases, including university students, nature-related cues may serve as nonverbal metaphors of renewal and moving toward the future.

The significant improvement in self-reported feeling of relaxation fits with the results of the studies by Ulrich. According to stress reduction theory, relaxation is a core prerequisite for cognitive restoration. Enhanced relaxation often leads to stress level reduction. The fight or flight state that accompanies stress is reduced and rest and digest state (parasympathetic system) support rapid stress recovery and strengthens emotional regulation [79]. Relax states ease attentional focus and engagement with the environment, enabling a more open and sustained focus [80]. This is very important, because it has been found that university students tend to experience stress due to academic pressures. The ability of digital ecotherapy intervention to promote relaxation is a promising pathway for alleviating the stress burden and helping the students restore their concentration as well as helping them with their academic performance. Student populations, who are typically under continuous academic pressure, will find the rise in relaxation to be particularly important. From the perspective of mental health promotion, improving relaxation helps to control emotions, lowers susceptibility to anxiety rise, and may work as a preventive element against academic burnout [81].

Mental fatigue is a psychobiological condition resulting from extended, taxing cognitive activity [82]. The load of cognitive tasks, especially prolonged ones, may cause mental fatigue [83]. As a result, mentally fatigued students may sometimes have difficulty maintaining directed attention in lectures and while studying [84]. That means that irrelevant stimuli may easily break their attention and lead to impaired performance [85]. Thus, it is imperative for the students to have under their disposal tools that can help them replenish their cognitive resources. Moreover, the phrase "Energy to spare" can also be interpreted as a deposit that is ready to be invested to important others, like friends and family, facilitating greater social networking and better interpersonal relationships. This is in convergence with studies that have found that group ecotherapeutic approaches build deeper social relationships [86].

The noted rise in self-reported energy shows a significant improvement in participants' subjective vitality, which is a key indication of psychological well-being across several theoretical models. Based on Self-Determination Theory (SDT), subjective vitality is the dynamic expression of mental and emotional well-being, the sensation of being alive, vigorous, and energetic [72]. It usually materializes when people feel autonomy, competence, and connectivity, all of which can be indirectly supported by the beneficial influence of natural environments. The rise in energy after exposure to nature in the present study is also aligned with the Attention Restoration Theory [25], which holds that nature restores depleted cognitive resources by means of gentle fascination and effortless attention. Such cognitive restoration can lead to more cognitive stamina and mental rejuvenation, both of which enhance the subjective feeling of having "energy to spare."

Moreover, according to the Broaden-and-Build Theory [71], pleasant emotions such as cheerfulness and relaxation tend to create lasting personal resources like vitality and physical drive. Therefore, the observed increase in energy can not only be a direct result of lower stress and better focus but also a by-product of improved emotional states caused by the nature-based stimuli.

The notable rise in self-reported cheerfulness implies that exposure to natural environments, whether real or simulated, could induce feelings of satisfaction, joy, and tranquility [2]. Being close to nature has been shown to improve mood, mental health and well-being, while a strong personal connection to nature appears to be linked to happiness [87]. People's mental health and positive effects are often improved if they feel more emotionally connected to nature [88]. Students that feel happy are more likely to interact socially, show warmth, and read ambiguous social signals in a prosocial manner-qualities that might enhance peer relationships, contribute to a more interactive and attentive classroom climate and increase a sense of academic belongingness [89]. Thus, in the context of the current study, the rise in cheerfulness may signal more than just a pleasant mood; it may represent a psychological readiness to reengage

with life, to find meaning in experience, and to connect emotionally with others. In this way, cheerfulness may be a “gateway affect,” opening the path toward deeper and more stable forms of well-being.

The shift between pre and post intervention mean scores on “I’ve been thinking clearly” may not have reached statistical significance, however it is noteworthy. Exposure to nature and images of nature, have been shown to have benefits on mood and stress, improving the attention and executive function, while the presence of natural elements has been associated with a clearer cognitive state [90]. Natural environments tend to allow the brain to rest and recover, they can improve concentration, memory and decision-making abilities [4].

Numerous research has shown that exposure to nature enhances attentional control, task persistence, and working memory [91]. Though the intervention in the current study did not produce a statistically significant change, the positive trend shown implies an early-stage effect on students reported cognitive sharpness, maybe enabled by slight attentional recalibration. Thinking with clarity is a major component in self-control, academic performance, and problem-solving confidence in the larger context of mental well-being [92].

Similarly to the previous variable, the “Feeling interested in other people” variable may not have been statistically significant, but it showed a considerable difference in the mean scores, which suggests that there may have been a noticeable shift in participant’s attitudes, regarding their interest in others. Exposure to nature can increase empathy and social interests by fostering a sense of connectedness with others and the environment [76]. After interacting with natural environments, even digital ones, participants may have become more interested in other people, which could be explained by this change.

The variable “Feeling confident” showed a noticeable difference in mean scores pre and post intervention. Although, the change was not statistically significant, there may be a valid scientific mechanism underlying the observed shift on participant’s attitudes. It is known that getting in touch with nature and greenspaces can increase happiness and self-esteem. Nature can create a safe space that allows people to feel emotionally balanced and grounded and therefore, positive emotions act as a link between nature and self-worth [92]. Though this item lacked statistical significance, the directional rise in self-reported confidence is notable given the greater psychological context. Confidence is the belief in one’s own strength to act successfully, solve problems, and face adversities, a fundamental element of self-efficacy [93] and psychological empowerment [94].

Regarding the interpretation of the GAD-7 questionnaire, according to the aforementioned analysis in the Methodology section, it should be kept in mind that GAD-7 is more effective in detecting the manifestation of general anxiety disorder in its clinical form and satisfying – but not as effective -in detecting various manifestations of anxiety symptoms [62]. So, it is possible that the intervention improved a range of anxiety symptoms that are not part of the diagnostic criteria of DSM-IV-TR for the clinical general anxiety disorder.

Participants showed a significant drop in their tendency to “Not being able to stop or control worrying”, even though the change did not reach statistical significance. Nonetheless, nature exposure can increase motivation and reduce stress. Studies have found that connection with nature can reduce risk of stress and improve negative feelings, fatigue and confusion.

One of the fundamental symptoms of generalized anxiety the feeling of unmanageable concern, which is not only common but also seen as intrusive and hard to control is captured by this GAD-7 item [95]. Given the date and context of the data gathering, the fact that the post-intervention score exhibited a decreasing trend, but not statistically significant, is important.

At the conclusion of the semester, when impending tests usually increase academic stress, the post-intervention evaluation was carried out [70]. Under normal circumstances, one would anticipate a rise in anxiety-related symptoms, including concern. The noted decline, then, points to a possible buffering impact of the ecotherapeutic treatment.

Theoretically speaking, executive functioning, emotional control, and attentional control have all been connected to unmanageable anxiety [96, 97]. Prefrontal cortical circuits that might become depleted under persistent stress facilitate these functions. Natural environments or maybe symbolic representations of nature exposure has been demonstrated to recover executive resources, enhance self-regulatory capacity, and break ruminative cycles [25, 73].

The mean scores before and after the intervention for “Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen”, increased significantly, indicating a reduction in fear and worry. Despite not being statistically significant, the shift suggests a

substantial trend. This finding supports the idea that spending time in nature reduces emotions of threat. According to this trend, nature-based interventions could improve emotional stability and a sense of safety [83].

From the standpoint of Stress Reduction Theory [72], exposure to natural stimuli such as the audiovisual components included in this intervention promotes physiological downregulation of arousal. This approach might reduce the somatic components of fear, like increased cortisol production, muscular tension, and faster heart rate. Furthermore, exposure to nature has been linked to a recalibration of danger evaluation mechanisms, which causes a transition from hypervigilant to reflective processing [25, 98]. This finding shows that when people are surrounded by peaceful, consistent external stimuli, their attention broadens, and the perceived dominance of internal danger signals diminishes.

The shift between the mean score for “Worrying too much about different things” was significantly increased, after the digital exposure to natural environment. Even though the change suggests a considerable trend in generalized worry, the shift was not statistically significant. Contact with nature may disrupt worrying thought patterns, by offering sights and sounds that draw the mind away from anxious thoughts [99]. This item captures a fundamental aspect of generalized anxiety: the feeling of constant, excessive concern in many areas of life—including scholastic achievement, relationships, economics, and health—often out of proportion to real dangers. Unlike targeted or situation-specific anxiety, this form of worry is generalized and spread out, hence causing persistent psychological pressure and cognitive overload.

Although not statistically significant, the little reduction seen in this symptom after the ecotherapeutic intervention might be functionally and theoretically relevant, especially when seen in the academic setting of the research. As mentioned, this second test was conducted near semester's end, when students usually see a rise in worry-related symptoms [74]. Thus, the absence of an increasing tendency in and of itself is proof of a buffering impact.

5. Conclusion

The present study explored the effects of a structured, low-intensity ecotherapeutic intervention consisting of audiovisual exposure to natural environments integrated into academic classrooms on university students' mental well-being and symptoms of generalized anxiety. Though not all results attained statistical significance, the intervention was linked to statistically significant changes in key fundamental aspects of mental well-being including relaxation, optimism, having energy to spare, and cheerfulness. Regarding anxiety, results from the GAD-7 demonstrated small but consistent reductions across all measured symptoms, including cognitive hyperactivity (e.g., “worrying too much about different things”), physiological arousal (e.g., “feeling nervous”), and anticipatory fear (e.g., “feeling afraid as if something awful might happen”). Particularly notable was the fact that these reductions occurred during the final weeks of the semester, a time typically associated with increased academic stress, due to the time proximity of the examinations of the semester. This suggests that the intervention may have exerted a stress-buffering function, contributing to emotional regulation during a period of heightened pressure.

The results of this study provide a practical framework for university administrators, public health professionals, and professors looking for affordable, scalable solutions to foster mental health in academic environments. Moreover, it's low-cost and time-efficient ecotherapeutic intervention under the limits of conventional classroom routines. Particularly in high-stress times like exam seasons, this implies that including nature-based stimuli—images, sounds, biophilic design—into educational settings might act as a preventative mental health approach. Such initiatives coincide with current WHO instructions on incorporating mental health promotion into everyday processes and support the argument for nature as a public health resource, not merely a recreational one. Given the simplicity and practicality of the intervention, academic institutions could think about creating “restorative learning environments” where natural aesthetics and multi-sensory ecotherapeutic cues are applied to improve attentional restoration, lower psychological load, and promote mental health and mental well-being.

Limitations

Although the present study offers valuable insights, a few limitations should be acknowledged. The absence of a control group limits the ability to definitively attribute the observed improvements to the intervention itself. Additionally, the sample consisted exclusively of university students, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations. The exclusive reliance on self-report questionnaires, while appropriate for the constructs measured, may be subject to response biases or limitations in self-awareness, a phenomenon that always is the case when using self-reported measures. Future studies are encouraged to include more diverse samples, employ experimental or longitudinal designs, and consider complementary assessment methods to strengthen the evidence base.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors proclaim no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The Author had taken the approval of the appropriate committee of ethical and deontology on research

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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